

NEUTROSOPHIC d -IDEAL OF NEUTROSOPHIC d -ALGEBRA

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Abstract: In this article, we introduce the concept of neutrosophic d -ideal of neutrosophic d -algebra. Also we have studied several properties of them. We also furnish some suitable examples.

Keywords: Fuzzy Set; Intuitionistic Fuzzy Set; Neutrosophic Set; d -Algebra; d -Ideal; d -Sub-Algebra.

1. Introduction:

The concept of BCK algebra and BCI algebra are introduced by Imai & Iseki [18]. Thereafter, Negger & Kim [23] introduced the d -algebra as a generalization of BCK algebra. Negger et al. [22] discussed the ideal theory in d -algebra. In the year 1965, Zadeh introduced the idea of fuzzy set [26]. Thereafter, Atanassov introduced the notion of intuitionistic fuzzy set [1], which is the natural generalization of fuzzy set. Later on, Jun et al. [20] applied the notion of intuitionistic fuzzy set on d -algebra. Afterwards, the notion of intuitionistic fuzzy d -ideal of d -algebra was introduced by Hasan [16] in 2017. Thereafter, the concept of intuitionistic fuzzy d -filter was introduced by Hasan [17] in 2020. The concept of neutrosophic set was introduced by Smarandache [24]. In this article, we procure the notion of neutrosophic d -algebra and neutrosophic d -ideal by extending the notion of intuitionistic fuzzy d -ideal of d -algebra.

Research gap: No investigation on neutrosophic d -algebra and neutrosophic d -ideal has been reported in the recent literature.

Motivation: To fill the research gap, we introduce the neutrosophic d -algebra and neutrosophic d -ideal.

The rest of the paper is designed as follows:

In section-2, we recall d -algebra, d -ideal, fuzzy d -algebra, fuzzy d -ideal, intuitionistic fuzzy d -algebra, intuitionistic fuzzy d -ideal. In section-3, we introduce the notion of neutrosophic d -algebra, neutrosophic d -ideal, and the proofs of some propositions, theorems on neutrosophic d -algebra, and neutrosophic d -ideal. In section-4, we give the conclusions of work done in this paper.

2. Preliminaries and Some Results:

Definition 2.1.[17] Assume that W be a non-empty set and 0 be a constant. Then, W with a binary operation $*$ is called a d -algebra if it satisfies the following three axioms:

- (i) $c * c = 0, \forall c \in W$
- (ii) $0 * c = 0, \forall c \in W$
- (iii) $c * d = 0$ and $d * c = 0 \Rightarrow c = d, \forall c, d \in W$.

We will refer to $c * d$ by cd . And $c \leq d$ iff $cd = 0$.

Definition 2.2.[17] A d -algebra W is called commutative if $c(cd) = d(dc), \forall c, d \in W$, and $d(dc)$ is denoted by $(c \wedge d)$.

Definition 2.3.[17] A d -algebra W is called bounded if there exist $a \in W$ such that $c \leq a$ for all $c \in W$, i.e. $ca = 0, \forall c \in W$.

Definition 2.4.[17] Let W be a d -algebra with binary operator $*$ and $A \subseteq W$. Then, A is said to be a d -sub-algebra of W , if $c, d \in A \Rightarrow cd \in A$.

Definition 2.5.[16] Let W be a d -algebra with binary operator $*$ and a constant 0 . Then, $D \subseteq W$ is called a d -ideal of W if it satisfies the following:

- (i) $a * b \in D$ and $b \in D \Rightarrow a \in D$;
- (ii) $a \in D$ and $b \in W \Rightarrow a * b \in D$.

Definition 2.6.[15] Let $Y = \{(c, T_Y(c)) : c \in W\}$ be a fuzzy set over a d -algebra W . Then, A is called a fuzzy d -algebra if $T_Y(cd) \geq \min\{T_Y(c), T_Y(d)\}$, for all $c, d \in W$.

Definition 2.7.[15] An fuzzy set $Y = \{(c, T_Y(c), F_Y(c)) : c \in W\}$ over a d -algebra W is called the fuzzy d -ideal if it satisfies the following inequalities:

- (i) $T_Y(c) \geq \min\{T_Y(cd), T_Y(d)\}$;
- (iii) $T_Y(cd) \geq T_Y(c)$, for all $c, d \in W$.

Definition 2.8.[14] Let $Y = \{(c, T_Y(c), F_Y(c)) : c \in W\}$ be an intuitionistic fuzzy set over a d -algebra W . Then, A is called an intuitionistic fuzzy d -algebra if it satisfies the followings:

- (i) $T_Y(cd) \geq \min\{T_Y(c), T_Y(d)\}$;
- (ii) $F_Y(cd) \leq \max\{F_Y(c), F_Y(d)\}$;

where $c, d \in W$.

Proposition 2.1.[14] Every intuitionistic fuzzy d -algebra $Y = \{(c, T_Y(c), F_Y(c)) : c \in W\}$ of W satisfies the following inequalities:

- (i) $T_Y(0) \geq T_Y(c)$, for all $c \in W$;
- (ii) $F_Y(0) \leq F_Y(c)$, for all $c \in W$.

Definition 2.9.[10] An intuitionistic fuzzy set $Y = \{(c, T_Y(c), F_Y(c)) : c \in W\}$ over a d -algebra W is called the intuitionistic fuzzy d -ideal if it satisfies the following inequalities:

- (i) $T_Y(c) \geq \min\{T_Y(cd), T_Y(d)\}$;
- (ii) $F_Y(c) \leq \max\{F_Y(cd), F_Y(d)\}$;
- (iii) $T_Y(cd) \geq T_Y(c)$;
- (iv) $F_Y(cd) \geq F_Y(c)$; for all $c, d \in Y$.

Proposition 2.2.[10] Let $Y = \{(c, T_Y(c), F_Y(c)) : c \in W\}$ be an intuitionistic fuzzy d -ideal over a d -algebra W . Then, the following inequalities hold:

$$T_Y(0) \geq T_Y(c), F_Y(0) \leq F_Y(c), \text{ for all } c \in W.$$

Definition 2.10.[18] A neutrosophic set over a universal set W is defined as follows:

$H = \{(y, T_H(y), I_H(y), F_H(y)) : y \in W\}$, where $T_H(y)$, $I_H(y)$ and $F_H(y)$ ($\in]0, 1^+[$) are the truth, indeterminacy and false membership value of y and $0 \leq T_H(y) + I_H(y) + F_H(y) \leq 3^+$.

Definition 2.11.[18] The neutrosophic whole set (1_N) and neutrosophic null set (0_N) over a universal set W is defined as follows:

(i) $1_N = \{(y, 1, 0, 0) : y \in W\}$.

(ii) $0_N = \{(y, 0, 0, 1) : y \in W\}$.

Definition 2.12.[18] Assume that $H = \{(y, T_H(y), I_H(y), F_H(y)) : y \in W\}$ and $K = \{(y, T_K(y), I_K(y), F_K(y)) : y \in W\}$ are any two neutrosophic sets over X . Then,

(i) $H \cup K = \{(y, T_H(y) \vee T_K(y), I_H(y) \wedge I_K(y), F_H(y) \wedge F_K(y)) : y \in W\}$;

(ii) $H \cap K = \{(y, T_H(y) \wedge T_K(y), I_H(y) \vee I_K(y), F_H(y) \vee F_K(y)) : y \in W\}$;

(iii) $H^c = \{(y, 1 - T_H(y), 1 - I_H(y), 1 - F_H(y)) : y \in W\}$;

(iv) $H \subseteq K \Leftrightarrow T_H(y) \leq T_K(y), I_H(y) \geq I_K(y), F_H(y) \geq F_K(y)$, for each $y \in W$.

3. Neutrosophic d -Algebra and Neutrosophic d -Ideal:

Definition 3.1. Let $Y = \{(c, T_Y(c), I_Y(c), F_Y(c)) : c \in W\}$ be an neutrosophic set over a d -algebra W . Then, A is called a neutrosophic d -algebra if it satisfies the followings:

(i) $T_Y(c * d) \geq \min\{T_Y(c), T_Y(d)\}$;

(ii) $I_Y(c * d) \leq \max\{I_Y(c), I_Y(d)\}$;

(iii) $F_Y(c * d) \leq \max\{F_Y(c), F_Y(d)\}$;

where $c, d \in W$.

Example 3.1. Take $W = \{0, c, d, w\}$ with the following table

\star	0	c	d	w
0	0	0	0	0
c	c	0	0	c
d	d	d	0	0
w	w	w	d	0

Note that if we define

$$T_Y(a) = \begin{cases} 0.2 & \text{if } a = 0, c \\ 0.02 & \text{if } a = d, w \end{cases}, I_Y(a) = \begin{cases} 0.09 & \text{if } a = 0, c \\ 0.8 & \text{if } a = d, w \end{cases} \text{ and } F_Y(a) = \begin{cases} 0.05 & \text{if } a = 0, c \\ 0.7 & \text{if } a = d, w \end{cases}$$

So we can show easily that $Y = \{(c, T_Y(c), I_Y(c), F_Y(c)) : c \in W\}$ is a neutrosophic d -algebra

Proposition 3.1. Every neutrosophic d -algebra $Y = \{(c, T_Y(c), I_Y(c), F_Y(c)) : c \in W\}$ of W satisfies the following inequalities:

(i) $T_Y(0) \geq T_Y(c)$, for all $c \in W$;

(ii) $I_Y(0) \leq I_Y(c)$, for all $c \in W$;

(iii) $F_Y(0) \leq F_Y(c)$, for all $c \in W$.

Proof. Assume that $Y = \{(c, T_Y(c), I_Y(c), F_Y(c)) : c \in W\}$ be a neutrosophic d -algebra of W . Let $c \in W$. Then

(i) $T_Y(0) = T_Y(c * c) \geq \min\{T_Y(c), T_Y(c)\} = T_Y(c)$, (using definition 2.1. & 3.1.)

(ii) $I_Y(0) = I_Y(c * c) \leq \max\{I_Y(c), I_Y(c)\} = I_Y(c)$, (using definition 2.1. & 3.1.)

(iii) $F_Y(0) = F_Y(c * c) \leq \max\{F_Y(c), F_Y(c)\} = F_Y(c)$, (using definition 2.1. & 3.1.)

Theorem 3.1. Let $\{Y_i : i \in \Delta\}$ be the family of neutrosophic d -algebra of W . Then, $\bigcap_{i \in \Delta} Y_i$ is a neutrosophic d -algebra of W .

Proof. Assume that $\{Y_i : i \in \Delta\}$ be the family of neutrosophic d -algebra of W . Now, $\bigcap_{i \in \Delta} Y_i = \{(c, \wedge T_{Y_i}(c), \vee I_{Y_i}(c), \vee F_{Y_i}(c)) : c \in W\}$. Let $c, d \in W$. Then,

(i) $\wedge T_{Y_i}(c * d) \geq \wedge \min\{T_{Y_i}(c), T_{Y_i}(d)\} = \min\{\wedge T_{Y_i}(c), \wedge T_{Y_i}(d)\}$

$\Rightarrow \wedge T_{Y_i}(c * d) \geq \min\{\wedge T_{Y_i}(c), \wedge T_{Y_i}(d)\}$;

(ii) $\vee I_{Y_i}(c * d) \leq \vee \max\{I_{Y_i}(c), I_{Y_i}(d)\} = \max\{\vee I_{Y_i}(c), \vee I_{Y_i}(d)\}$

$\Rightarrow \vee I_{Y_i}(c * d) \leq \max\{\vee I_{Y_i}(c), \vee I_{Y_i}(d)\}$;

(iii) $\vee F_{Y_i}(c * d) \leq \vee \max\{F_{Y_i}(c), F_{Y_i}(d)\} = \max\{\vee F_{Y_i}(c), \vee F_{Y_i}(d)\}$

$\Rightarrow \vee F_{Y_i}(c * d) \leq \max\{\vee F_{Y_i}(c), \vee F_{Y_i}(d)\}$;

Therefore, $\bigcap_{i \in \Delta} Y_i$ is also a neutrosophic d -algebra of W .

Theorem 3.3. If $Y = \{(c, T_Y(c), I_Y(c), F_Y(c)) : c \in W\}$ is a neutrosophic d -algebra of W , then the sets $W_T = \{c \in W : T_Y(c) = T_Y(0)\}$, $W_I = \{c \in W : I_Y(c) = I_Y(0)\}$, and $W_F = \{c \in W : F_Y(c) = F_Y(0)\}$ are d -sub-algebras of W .

Proof. Assume that $Y = \{(c, T_Y(c), I_Y(c), F_Y(c)) : c \in W\}$ be a neutrosophic d -algebra of W . Given $W_T = \{c \in W : T_Y(c) = T_Y(0)\}$, $W_I = \{c \in W : I_Y(c) = I_Y(0)\}$, and $W_F = \{c \in W : F_Y(c) = F_Y(0)\}$. Let $c, d \in W_T$. Therefore, $T_Y(c) = T_Y(0)$, $T_Y(d) = T_Y(0)$. Now by definition 2.1, $T_Y(c * d) \geq \min\{T_Y(c), T_Y(d)\} = \min\{T_Y(0), T_Y(0)\} = T_Y(0)$, i.e. $T_Y(c * d) \geq T_Y(0)$. Again from proposition 3.1, it is clear that $T_Y(0) \leq T_Y(c * d)$. Therefore $T_Y(c * d) = T_Y(0)$. This implies that $c * d \in W_T$. Hence $c, d \in W_T \Rightarrow c * d \in W_T$. Therefore the set $W_T = \{c \in W : T_Y(c) = T_Y(0)\}$ is a d -sub-algebra of W .

Similarly we can easily show that $W_I = \{c \in W : I_Y(c) = I_Y(0)\}$ and $W_F = \{c \in W : F_Y(c) = F_Y(0)\}$ are d -sub-algebras of W .

Definition 3.2. Assume that $Y = \{(c, T_Y(c), I_Y(c), F_Y(c)) : c \in W\}$ be a neutrosophic set over W . Then, the sets $W(T_Y, \alpha) = \{c \in W : T_Y(c) \geq \alpha\}$, $W(I_Y, \alpha) = \{c \in W : I_Y(c) \leq \alpha\}$, $W(F_Y, \alpha) = \{c \in W : F_Y(c) \leq \alpha\}$ are respectively called T -level α -cut, I -level α -cut, F -level α -cut of Y .

Theorem 3.4. Assume that $Y = \{(c, T_Y(c), I_Y(c), F_Y(c)) : c \in W\}$ be a neutrosophic d -algebra of W . Then, for any $\alpha \in [0, 1]$, the T -level α -cut, I -level α -cut, F -level α -cut of Y are d -sub-algebra of W .

Proof. Assume that $Y = \{(c, T_Y(c), I_Y(c), F_Y(c)) : c \in W\}$ be a neutrosophic d -algebra of W . Then, T -level α -cut of $Y = W(T_Y, \alpha) = \{c \in W : T_Y(c) \geq \alpha\}$, I -level α -cut of $Y = W(I_Y, \alpha) = \{c \in W : I_Y(c) \leq \alpha\}$, and F -level α -cut of $Y = W(F_Y, \alpha) = \{c \in W : F_Y(c) \leq \alpha\}$.

Let $c, d \in W(T_Y, \alpha)$. Therefore, $T_Y(c) \geq \alpha$, $T_Y(d) \geq \alpha$. Now $T_Y(c * d) \geq \min\{T_Y(c), T_Y(d)\} \geq \min\{\alpha, \alpha\} \geq \alpha$. This implies, $c * d \in W(T_Y, \alpha)$. Hence, $c, d \in W(T_Y, \alpha) \Rightarrow c * d \in W(T_Y, \alpha)$. Therefore, $W(T_Y, \alpha)$ i.e. T -level α -cut of Y is a d -sub-algebra of W .

Similarly, we can easily show that I -level α -cut, F -level α -cut of Y are d -sub-algebra of W .

Definition 3.3. An neutrosophic set $Y = \{(c, T_Y(c), I_Y(c), F_Y(c)) : c \in W\}$ over a d -algebra W is called a neutrosophic d -ideal if it satisfies the following inequalities:

- (i) $T_Y(c) \geq \min\{T_Y(cd), T_Y(d)\}$;
- (ii) $F_Y(c) \leq \max\{F_Y(cd), F_Y(d)\}$;
- (iii) $I_Y(c) \leq \max\{I_Y(cd), I_Y(d)\}$;
- (iv) $T_Y(cd) \geq T_Y(c)$;
- (v) $F_Y(cd) \geq F_Y(c)$;
- (vi) $I_Y(cd) \geq I_Y(c)$, for all $c, d \in Y$.

Example 3.2. Take $W = \{0, c, d, w\}$ with the following table

*	0	c	d
0	0	0	0
c	d	0	d
d	c	c	0

Note that if we define

$$T_Y(a) = \begin{cases} 0.9 & \text{if } a = 0 \\ 0.01 & \text{if } a = c, d \end{cases}, \quad I_Y(a) = \begin{cases} 0.1 & \text{if } a = 0 \\ 0.5 & \text{if } a = c, d \end{cases} \quad \text{and} \quad F_Y(a) = \begin{cases} 0.2 & \text{if } a = 0 \\ 0.6 & \text{if } a = c, d \end{cases}$$

Then $Y = \{(c, T_Y(c), I_Y(c), F_Y(c)) : c \in W\}$ is a neutrosophic d -ideal of d -algebra

Proposition 3.2. If $Y = \{(c, T_Y(c), I_Y(c), F_Y(c)) : c \in W\}$ is a neutrosophic d -ideal of W , then $T_Y(0) \geq T_Y(c)$, $I_Y(0) \leq I_Y(c)$, $F_Y(0) \leq F_Y(c)$, for all $c \in W$.

Proof. Assume that $Y = \{(c, T_Y(c), I_Y(c), F_Y(c)) : c \in W\}$ is a neutrosophic d -ideal of W , and c be any arbitrary element of W . Since $T_Y(c*c) \geq T_Y(c)$, so $T_Y(0) \geq T_Y(c)$. Similarly, since $I_Y(c*c) \leq I_Y(c)$, so $I_Y(0) \leq I_Y(c)$. Again, since $F_Y(c*c) \leq F_Y(c)$, so $F_Y(0) \leq F_Y(c)$.

Theorem 3.6. Assume that $Y = \{(x, T_Y(x), I_Y(x), F_Y(x)) : x \in W\}$ is a neutrosophic d -ideal of W . If $x*y \leq z$, then $T_Y(x) \geq \min\{T_Y(y), T_Y(z)\}$, $I_Y(x) \leq \max\{I_Y(y), I_Y(z)\}$, $F_Y(x) \leq \max\{F_Y(y), F_Y(z)\}$.

Proof. Assume that $Y = \{(x, T_Y(x), I_Y(x), F_Y(x)) : x \in W\}$ be an neutrosophic d -ideal of W . Let x, y, z be any three element of W such that $x*y \leq z$. Then by definition 2.1, $(x*y)*z = 0$.

Now, $T_Y(x) \geq \min\{T_Y(x*y), T_Y(y)\} \geq \min\{\min\{T_Y((x*y)*z), T_Y(z)\}, T_Y(y)\} = \min\{\min\{T_Y(0), T_Y(z)\}, T_Y(y)\} \geq \min\{T_Y(z), T_Y(y)\}$. Therefore, $T_Y(x) \geq \min\{T_Y(y), T_Y(z)\}$.

Now, $I_Y(x) \leq \max\{I_Y(x*y), I_Y(y)\} \leq \max\{\max\{I_Y((x*y)*z), I_Y(z)\}, I_Y(y)\} = \max\{\max\{I_Y(0), I_Y(z)\}, I_Y(y)\} \leq \max\{I_Y(z), I_Y(y)\}$. Therefore, $I_Y(x) \leq \max\{I_Y(y), I_Y(z)\}$.

Again, $F_Y(x) \leq \max\{F_Y(x*y), F_Y(y)\} \leq \max\{\max\{F_Y((x*y)*z), F_Y(z)\}, F_Y(y)\} = \max\{\max\{F_Y(0), F_Y(z)\}, F_Y(y)\} \leq \max\{F_Y(z), F_Y(y)\}$. Therefore, $F_Y(x) \leq \max\{F_Y(y), F_Y(z)\}$.

Theorem 3.7. Assume that $Y = \{(c, T_Y(c), I_Y(c), F_Y(c)) : c \in W\}$ is a neutrosophic d -ideal of W . If $x \leq z$, then $T_Y(x) \geq T_Y(z)$, $I_Y(x) \leq I_Y(z)$, $F_Y(x) \leq F_Y(z)$.

Proof. Assume that $Y = \{(c, T_Y(c), I_Y(c), F_Y(c)) : c \in W\}$ is a neutrosophic d -ideal of W . Also let x, z be any two element of W such that $x \leq z$. Then by the definition 2.1, $x*z = 0$.

Now, $T_Y(x) \geq \min\{T_Y(x*z), T_Y(z)\} = \min\{T_Y(0), T_Y(z)\}$, $T_Y(z) = T_Y(z)$. Therefore, $T_Y(x) \geq T_Y(z)$.

Now, $I_Y(x) \leq \max\{I_Y(x*z), I_Y(z)\} = \max\{I_Y(0), I_Y(z)\}$, $I_Y(z) = I_Y(z)$. Therefore, $I_Y(x) \leq I_Y(z)$.

Now, $F_Y(x) \leq \max\{F_Y(x * z), F_Y(z)\} = \max\{F_Y(0), F_Y(z)\}$, $F_Y(z) = F_Y(z)$. Therefore, $F_Y(x) \leq F_Y(z)$.

Theorem 3.10. If $\{D_i: i \in \Delta\}$ be the collection of neutrosophic d -ideals of d -algebra W , then $\bigcap_{i \in \Delta} D_i$ is also a neutrosophic d -ideal of d -algebra W .

Proof. Assume that $\{D_i: i \in \Delta\}$ be the collection of neutrosophic d -ideals of d -algebra W . We have $\bigcap_{i \in \Delta} D_i = \{(c, \wedge T_{Y_i}(c), \vee I_{Y_i}(c), \vee F_{Y_i}(c)): c \in W\}$.

Now $\wedge T_{Y_i}(c) \geq \wedge \{\min\{T_{Y_i}(c * d), T_{Y_i}(d)\}\} \geq \min\{\wedge T_{Y_i}(c * d), \wedge T_{Y_i}(d)\}$,

$\vee I_{Y_i}(c) \leq \vee \{\max\{I_{Y_i}(c * d), I_{Y_i}(d)\}\} \leq \max\{\vee I_{Y_i}(c * d), \vee I_{Y_i}(d)\}$,

and $\vee F_{Y_i}(c) \leq \vee \{\max\{F_{Y_i}(c * d), F_{Y_i}(d)\}\} \leq \max\{\vee F_{Y_i}(c * d), \vee F_{Y_i}(d)\}$.

Since $T_{Y_i}(c * d) \geq T_{Y_i}(c)$, $I_{Y_i}(c * d) \leq I_{Y_i}(c)$, $F_{Y_i}(c * d) \leq F_{Y_i}(c)$, for all i , we have $\wedge T_{Y_i}(c * d) \geq \wedge T_{Y_i}(c)$, $\vee I_{Y_i}(c * d) \leq \vee I_{Y_i}(c)$, $\vee F_{Y_i}(c * d) \leq \vee F_{Y_i}(c)$, for all i . Hence $\bigcap_{i \in \Delta} D_i = \{(c, \wedge T_{Y_i}(c), \vee I_{Y_i}(c), \vee F_{Y_i}(c)): c \in W\}$ is a neutrosophic d -ideal of W .

Theorem 3.11. A neutrosophic set $Y = \{(c, T_Y(c), F_Y(c), I_Y(c)): c \in W\}$ is neutrosophic d -ideal of d -algebra W if and only if the corresponding fuzzy set $\{(c, T_Y(c)): c \in W\}$, $\{(c, 1 - I_Y(c)): c \in W\}$, $\{(c, 1 - F_Y(c)): c \in W\}$ are fuzzy d -ideal of W .

Proof. Assume that $Y = \{(c, T_Y(c), F_Y(c), I_Y(c)): c \in W\}$ be a neutrosophic d -ideal of W . Therefore for all $c, d \in W$, $T_Y(c) \geq \min\{T_Y(cd), T_Y(d)\}$; $T_Y(cd) \geq T_Y(c)$; $I_Y(c) \leq \max\{I_Y(cd), I_Y(d)\}$; $I_Y(cd) \leq I_Y(c)$; $F_Y(c) \leq \max\{F_Y(cd), F_Y(d)\}$; $F_Y(cd) \leq F_Y(c)$.

Since for all $c, d \in W$, $T_Y(c) \geq \min\{T_Y(cd), T_Y(d)\}$; $T_Y(cd) \geq T_Y(c)$, so the fuzzy set $\{(c, T_Y(c)): c \in W\}$ is a fuzzy d -ideal of W .

Now, for all $c, d \in W$,

$I_Y(c) \leq \max\{I_Y(cd), I_Y(d)\} \Rightarrow 1 - I_Y(c) \geq \min\{1 - I_Y(cd), 1 - I_Y(d)\}$;

$I_Y(cd) \leq I_Y(c) \Rightarrow 1 - I_Y(cd) \geq 1 - I_Y(c)$;

Therefore, the fuzzy set $\{(c, 1 - I_Y(c)): c \in W\}$ is a fuzzy d -ideal of W .

Again, for all $c, d \in W$,

$F_Y(c) \leq \max\{F_Y(cd), F_Y(d)\} \Rightarrow 1 - F_Y(c) \geq \min\{1 - F_Y(cd), 1 - F_Y(d)\}$;

$F_Y(cd) \leq F_Y(c) \Rightarrow 1 - F_Y(cd) \geq 1 - F_Y(c)$;

Therefore, the fuzzy set $\{(c, 1 - F_Y(c)): c \in W\}$ is a fuzzy d -ideal of W .

Hence for an neutrosophic d -ideal $Y = \{(c, T_Y(c), F_Y(c), I_Y(c)): c \in W\}$ of W , the corresponding fuzzy sets $\{(c, T_Y(c)): c \in W\}$, $\{(c, 1 - I_Y(c)): c \in W\}$, $\{(c, 1 - F_Y(c)): c \in W\}$ are fuzzy d -ideal of W .

Theorem 3.12. If a neutrosophic set $Y = \{(c, T_Y(c), F_Y(c), I_Y(c)): c \in W\}$ is neutrosophic d -ideal of d -algebra W , then the sets $W(T_Y) = \{c \in W: T_Y(c) = T_Y(0)\}$, $W(I_Y) = \{c \in W: I_Y(c) = I_Y(0)\}$, and $W(F_Y) = \{c \in W: F_Y(c) = F_Y(0)\}$ are d -ideal of W .

Proof. Assume that $Y = \{(c, T_Y(c), F_Y(c), I_Y(c)): c \in W\}$ be a neutrosophic d -ideal of a d -algebra W .

Let $a * b \in W(T_Y)$ and $b \in W(T_Y)$. Therefore, $T_Y(a * b) = T_Y(0)$ and $T_Y(b) = T_Y(0)$. Since Y is a neutrosophic d -ideal of a d -algebra W , so $T_Y(a) \geq \min\{T_Y(a * b), T_Y(b)\} = \min\{T_Y(0), T_Y(0)\} = T_Y(0)$. This implies that $T_Y(a) \geq T_Y(0)$. Again by proposition 3.2, it is clear that $T_Y(0) \geq T_Y(a)$. Hence $T_Y(a) = T_Y(0)$, i.e. $a \in W(T_Y)$. Therefore, $a * b \in W(T_Y)$ and $b \in W(T_Y) \Rightarrow a \in W(T_Y)$.

Again let $a \in W(T_Y)$ and $b \in W$. Therefore, $T_Y(a) = T_Y(0)$. Since Y is a neutrosophic d -ideal of a d -algebra W , so $T_Y(a * b) \geq T_Y(a) = T_Y(0)$. This implies that $T_Y(a * b) \geq T_Y(0)$. From proposition 3.2, it is clear that $T_Y(0) \geq$

$T_Y(a*b)$. Hence $T_Y(a*b)=T_Y(0)$, i.e. $a*b \in W(T_Y)$. Therefore, $a \in W(T_Y)$ and $b \in W \Rightarrow a*b \in W(T_Y)$. Hence the set $W(T_Y)=\{c \in W: T_Y(c)=T_Y(0)\}$ is a d -ideal of W .

Similarly we can show that, the sets $W(I_Y)=\{c \in W: I_Y(c)=I_Y(0)\}$, and $W(F_Y)=\{c \in W: F_Y(c)=F_Y(0)\}$ are d -ideal of W .

5. Conclusions:

In this article, we introduce the notion of neutrosophic d -ideals of d -algebra. Further we have investigated different properties and study some relations on neutrosophic d -algebra. By defining neutrosophic d -algebra, neutrosophic d -ideals, we prove some propositions, theorems on neutrosophic d -algebra and d -ideal.

In the future, we hope that many new notions namely neutrosophic d -filter, neutrosophic d -topology can be introduce based on these notions of neutrosophic d -algebra.

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